

ONLINE EVENT

06 Jul 2023

10:00 - 11:15 (CEST)

SAVE THE DATE

Harnessing the Potential of Smart Technologies and Local Digital Twins for the New European Bauhaus

digiNEB.eu
digital ecosystem for the New European Bauhaus

- 10:00 Welcome and introduction, **Maria Giuffrida**, *Trust-IT*
- 10:10 DS4SSCC objectives and main results, **Sophie Meszaros**, *OASC*
- 10:20 Living-in.eu objectives and main results - **Gabriela Ruseva**, *EuroCities*
- 10:30 Panel discussion «Adopting Smart Technologies and Local Digital Twins for Sustainable Communities»
 - **Marcos Nogueira**, *AURORAL*
 - **Guglielmo Ricciardi**, *PoliTO*
 - **Cristina Labianca**, *Sustainable Architecture Designer*
 - *Moderation and interaction with the audience* **Maria Giuffrida**, *Trust-IT*
- 11:00 Q&A
- 11:15 Conclusion

Who is joining the webinar today

Representatives of the NEB and digital world...

Who is joining the webinar today

... from more than 20 countries!

If you want to learn something more about digiNEB.eu

<https://youtu.be/tqVrPHnwG5s>

<https://youtu.be/cQI9zqq1uLk>

<https://youtu.be/wwJcRfta7tM>

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Watch the recordings from our previous webinars and follow digiNEB.eu to learn more about its journey!

Before starting...

- This session will be **recorded**
 - The recording will be available to all participants after the event
- Get engaged by
 - Asking questions via the **Q&A function** anytime during the event
 - Writing **comments in the chat**
 - **Raising your hand** if you want to comment via audio/video
 - Joining an **interactive session on menti.com**

Trust-IT Services
communicating to markets

- Project Coordinator
- Dissemination & Communication

COMMpla
Communication Platforms and Online Solutions

- COMMpla (AE) Platform manager

TU Delft

- Official NEB Partner
- Domain knowledge
- Digital catalogue
- TWGs

INDUSTRY COMMONS

- Community building
- Pan-European synergies
- NEB High Level Round Table membership

AAEE European Association for Architectural Education
Association Européenne pour l'Enseignement de l'Architecture

- Official NEBC Partner
- Capacity building
- Community

INNOVAWOOD

- Official NEB Partner
- Community
- Digitising EU Wood Industry

OBJECTIVES

Mission: To create the pan-European digital ecosystem supporting the New European Bauhaus (NEB) initiative.

Objective 1: Map & showcase existing digital solutions, projects and tools

Objective 2: Create an active network

Objective 3: Produce capacity building material

Objective 4: Issue recommendations and a NEB Digital Deployment roadmap

COMMUNITY

- 3000+ engaged community members across all Stakeholder Groups
- 500+ DB of R&I projects with digital solutions transferrable to the NEB environment
- 250+ digital solutions mapped & part of the digiNEB.eu toolkit
- 7000+ social media followers

SYNERGIES

- 100+ synergies with National, European, and Int'l organisations and initiatives
- Continuous engagement and exchanges on all NEB topics
- Regular interactions with relevant EC Offices
- Permanent NEB task force (w/NEB)

OUTREACH

- 6 Workshops
- 2 EAG strategic meetings
- 18 Webinars
- 21 newsletters
- 2 Yearly events
- 24 Professional Videos
- 6+ Marketing campaigns
- Visibility at third party events

REPORTS & OTHER VALUE-ADD INFO

- 1000+ certified trainees on digiNEB.eu
- 100+ members of the Early Adopters Network
- Success stories
- 4 policy briefs
- NEB Digital Deployment roadmap
- Landscape & Gap Analysis reports

The opportunities we offer

Find the digital solution you need

100+ uploaded solutions

Submit your NEB story

20+ success stories

Join discussions

4 Thematic Working Groups

Training material

11 Courses

Become an "Early Adopter"

10+ Published Profiles

thank you for your attention!

The digiNEB.eu Consortium:
TU-DELFT, Trust-IT, COMMpla,
Industry Commons, European Association for
Architectural Education, InnovaWood

www.digineb.eu

info@digineb.eu

